

Supporting Information for

Machine-learning identified molecular fragments of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons
responsible for interstellar infrared emission bands

README For Supplementary Example Code File

- Description of contents:
 - The files in the ./example_code/ directory contain an example code of Machine Learning and input files. RF_importance.py is an executable Python script, which performs training and feature importance calculations by directly running this code. The output files will be saved in ./result/, an automatically created folder.
- Code name: RF_importance.py
- Language: Python 3.7
- System requirements:
 - sklearn
 - json
 - numpy
 - pandas
- Description of input data:
 - Dataset.json : Molecular infrared spectrum dataset. This is a JSON format file that can be generated and read by “json” package.
 - ECFPs.json : Molecular fingerprint information dataset. This is a JSON format file that can be generated and read by “json” package.